

1 ***Nosema* spp. infection and its negative effects on honey bees (*Apis mellifera***
2 ***iberiensis*) at the colony level**

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23 **Abstract**

24 Nosemosis caused by the microsporidia *Nosema apis* and *Nosema ceranae* are
25 among the most common pathologies affecting adult honey bees. *N. apis* infection
26 has been associated with a reduced lifespan of infected bees and increased winter
27 mortality, and its negative impact on colony strength and productivity has been
28 described in several studies. By contrast, when the effects of nosemosis type C,
29 that caused by *N. ceranae* infection, have been analyzed at the colony level, these
30 studies have largely focused on collapse as a response to infection without
31 addressing the potential sub-clinical effects on colony strength and productivity.
32 Given the spread and prevalence of *N. ceranae* worldwide, we set out here to
33 characterize the sub-clinical and clinical signs of *N. ceranae* infection on colony
34 strength and productivity. Over a one year period, we evaluated the evolution of
35 50 honey bee colonies naturally infected by *Nosema* (mainly *N. ceranae*). Under
36 our experimental conditions, *N. ceranae* infection was highly pathogenic for
37 honey bee colonies, producing significant reductions in colony size, brood rearing
38 and honey production. These deleterious effects at the colony level may affect
39 beekeeping profitability and have serious consequences for pollination. Further
40 research is necessary to identify possible treatments or beekeeping techniques that
41 will limit the rapid spread of this dangerous emerging disease.

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43 **Keywords:** *Nosema ceranae*, sub-clinical signs, clinical signs, colony strength,
44 honey production.

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47 **1. Introduction**

48 Honey bees are key generalist pollinators that live in large perennial colonies,
49 ensuring high levels of local pollination throughout the flowering season. These
50 Hymenoptera can cover a vast foraging area, thereby enhancing gene flow in plant
51 communities [1-3] and playing an important role in crop pollination [4-6]. *A.*
52 *mellifera* considerably contributes to general crop pollination, the benefits of
53 which are substantially higher than those resulting from honey production [7].
54 However, it has been suggested that, on a global level, honey bees are primarily
55 reared to produce honey and other marketable products and thus, the economics of
56 honey production influence the global dynamics of bee management more than
57 their influence on agricultural and biological pollination [4,8]. Honey is by far the
58 most common and best known product from honey bee colonies, both from the
59 quantitative and economic point of view [9,10], and it represents an essential
60 commodity worldwide which adds nutritional variety to human diets [8]. Honey
61 production and trade is one of the important sources of finance in the world, with
62 global production in 2007 reaching 1.07 million tonnes [11]. In Spain, which has
63 the largest number of bee colonies, the highest honey production and the second
64 largest population of professional beekeepers after Greece from the European
65 Union [12], honey production was estimated at 31,800 thousand tonnes. Based on
66 the average price of honey in Spain in 2007 (€ 2,377 per tonne) [13], this activity
67 is valued at approximately € 75.7 million. Given these figures, it is clear that any

68 loss in honey production is an important concern for professional beekeepers,
69 particularly in the most productive countries.

70 Several factors affect honey production in the colony, including weather
71 conditions [14-16], the availability of adequate foraging resources [17] and colony
72 strength (*i.e.* brood production, size of the adult bee population, worker bee life
73 expectancy and the individual productivity of workers) [18-20].

74 Honey bee parasites and pathogens have also been reported to negatively
75 influence colony productivity [21-24], and some of the most damaging diseases of
76 adult honey bees are varroosis caused by the mite *Varroa destructor* [25,26], and
77 microsporidiosis caused by the spore-forming microsporidia *Nosema apis* and
78 *Nosema ceranae* [27-30]. Both these microsporidian species infect the midgut
79 (ventriculus) of the honey bees' digestive tract, although they cause two different
80 diseases, with distinct epidemiological, clinical and pathological characteristics
81 [10,31]. Despite the relatively recent discovery of *N. ceranae* infection in *A.*
82 *mellifera* [32,33], the number of studies analyzing the impact of *N. ceranae*
83 infection (namely Nosemosis type C) on honey bees at the individual level has
84 increased markedly [34-41]. The effect of nosemosis type C at the colony level
85 has also been evaluated [28,42,43], primarily focusing on the possible colony
86 collapse in response to infection, and disregarding the potential sub-clinical
87 effects on parameters such as colony strength and productivity. As several studies
88 have described negative impacts of *N. apis* infection on these colony parameters
89 [19,21,23,31,44-45], and in the light of the high prevalence of *N. ceranae*
90 worldwide [31,46], we sought to identify the clinical and sub-clinical signs of

91 *Nosema* infection on colony strength and productivity when *N. ceranae* is the
92 dominant species, which may affect beekeeping profitability and the efficiency of
93 honey bee pollination.

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95 **2. Materials and Methods**

96 **2.1. Honey bee colonies.**

97 In this study, 50 homogeneous colonies of *Apis mellifera iberiensis* in the
98 experimental apiaries located at the “Centro Apícola de Marchamalo” (CAR)
99 were monitored monthly from September 2007 to December 2008. Thereafter, the
100 presence/absence of the queen, colony mortality and clinical and sub-clinical
101 signs of any pathology were recorded each month until December 2010. All
102 colonies were acquired as nuclei (5 combs with worker bees and a queen) from
103 the same professional beekeeper in April 2007, and they were left to develop and
104 adapt to the field conditions of the study until June 2007, when they were
105 introduced into the new hives. At the start of the study, all the colonies were
106 negative for *Nosema* spp., *Varroa destructor*, American Foulbrood, European
107 Foulbrood and Chalkbrood, and they had a homogeneous worker population,
108 brood area and stored food. Brood diseases (American Foulbrood, European
109 Foulbrood and Chalkbrood disease) were evaluated by confirming the lack of
110 clinical signs, and the absence of *V. destructor* and *Nosema* spp. in the colonies
111 was recognized after analysis according to OIE methods [47] and Martín-
112 Hernández et al. [48] respectively.

113 The areas surrounding the hives contained no genetically modified agricultural
114 crops, and no insecticides such as fipronil or imidacloprid were in use.

115 The colonies were placed close to another apiary containing colonies naturally
116 parasitized by *N. ceranae* and/or *N. apis*, which acted as a natural source of
117 infection.

118 *V. destructor* parasitization was controlled twice a year (Apivar® a.m. amitraz) to
119 avoid the negative effects of this parasite on colony health.

120 **2.2. Field Assay Procedure**

121 Upon detection of *Nosema* spp. in September 2007 in all 50 colonies (100% *N.*
122 *ceranae*-positive; 50% co-infected with *N. apis*, Supplementary data Figure 1),
123 the colonies were randomly assigned to 5 experimental groups, each containing 10
124 colonies distributed in two different apiaries to reduce the risk of reinfection with
125 *Nosema* spp. of the treated colonies through the contact with the untreated ones.
126 Both apiaries were situated 500 m far from one another and at a similar altitude
127 (Apiary 1: 722 meters; Apiary 2: 720 meters), being surrounded by the same type
128 of flora (degradation stage of holm oak-Aleppo pine forest surrounded by cereal
129 crops; Supplementary Data Figure S2). In Apiary 1 (40°40'45.18''N,
130 3°13'1.01''W), 3 experimental groups were treated for infection by *Nosema* spp.
131 (Fumidil-B®; 4 doses of 30 mg fumagillin per colony administered at one week
132 intervals: [49]). Accordingly and as summarized in Table 1, colonies of group 1T
133 received one treatment (Autumn 2007), those of group 2T were treated twice
134 (Autumn 2007/Spring 2008), while group 4T received one treatment per season
135 (Autumn 2007/Winter 2008/Spring 2008/Summer 2008). In Apiary 2 (untreated

136 colonies; 40°40'59.25"N, 3°12'54.65"W), two experimental groups were
137 established: colonies of group CS received one application of sugar syrup
138 (vehicle; 1:1 distilled water-sugar) each season (Autumn 2007/Winter
139 2008/Spring 2008/Summer 2008), while group C (control group) was made up of
140 10 unmanaged colonies. Due to the random separation of the 50 colonies in 5
141 groups, the co-infected colonies (50% of the total) were not equally distributed
142 within the groups (see Supplementary Data Figure S1), but all groups contained
143 between 3 and 6 co-infected colonies.

144 Both sugar-syrup and fumagillin were administered in plastic bags placed over the
145 brood chamber and their consumption was assessed weekly [49]. Fumagillin
146 consumption was calculated on the basis of 30 mg fumagillin per 250 ml syrup
147 ingested. On the day a new dose was administered, the remaining unconsumed
148 doses were removed from the colony and weighed.

149 From September 2007 until December 2010, clinical signs indicative of
150 pathologies other than *Nosema* disease, the presence of a queen and colony
151 mortality were recorded on each visit to the apiaries (Table 1).

152 **2.3. Monitoring of *Nosema* spp. infection in the experimental colonies**

153 **2.3.1. Detection of infection (composite samples)**

154 To evaluate *Nosema* spp. infection in the colonies, samples of forager bees ($n \geq 30$
155 bees per sample) and house bees ($n \geq 30$ bees) were collected at noon, as
156 described previously [50]. Forager bee samples were collected 10 times,
157 approximately once a month, between September 2007 and December 2008
158 (Table 1). House bee samples were only collected before and after the

159 interventions in autumn 2007 and spring 2008. DNA was extracted from the
160 composite samples collected and PCR was performed as described previously
161 [51].

162 **2.3.2. Percentage of infected bees before and after interventions**

163 The percentage of worker bees infected by *Nosema* spp. was also evaluated in
164 each colony before and after the interventions in autumn 2007 and spring 2008 in
165 order to determine the effect of the different interventions on the evolution of
166 *Nosema* spp. infection at the beginning of the assay (autumn) and during the
167 period of most activity in the colonies (spring) [52]. Samples of forager bees ($n \geq$
168 20) and house bees ($n \geq 20$) were collected from each colony as described above,
169 one week before the first dose of treatment and two weeks after the last dose
170 (Table 1).

171 For forager bee samples, the percentage of infected bees was determined by
172 individual PCR analysis of the 20 forager bees from each of the studied colonies,
173 following the procedures described in a previous assay [51].

174 For house bees, the percentage of infected bees was determined in randomly
175 selected colonies that remained infected after the interventions, using the same
176 laboratory methods described above for forager bees.

177 **2.4. Colony strength**

178 The adult bee population and brood production (*i.e.* uncapped and capped brood)
179 were evaluated throughout the assay (from October 2007 to December 2008,
180 Table 1) by analyzing the frames covered by bees and quantifying the number of
181 brood cells [28,53]. Both the adult bee population and the number of brood cells

182 were evaluated each month (except for the months of December 2007, and March
183 and September 2008), a total of 12 measurements.

184 The proportion of brood cells (NC) to the number of combs covered by bees (P)
185 was also calculated to determine the ratio of brood to bees (NC/P).

186 **2.5. Honey production**

187 The honey production of each colony was evaluated at the harvesting season
188 (September 2008) by separately weighing all the frames with honey from each
189 colony and calculating the total amount of honey stored in them from the
190 difference in comb weight before and after honey extraction [52]. Only those
191 colonies alive at the harvesting season were used for the analysis.

192 **2.6. Statistical analysis**

193 Dependent variables studied were: percentage of infected bees, adult honey
194 bee population, number of brood cells, proportion of brood cells per bee
195 combs and honey production. They were normalized with linear
196 transformations. Two factors were taken into account, one fixed factor
197 (group) and the time effect. We ran Generalized Estimation Equations with
198 probability distribution normal, link function identity, subject effect colony and
199 within-subject effect time point.

200 Since the presence of interaction in the model revealed that the effects of
201 interventions varied with time effect, the mean values of the different
202 parameters (percentage of infected bees, adult honey bee population, number
203 of brood cells and proportion of brood cells per bee combs) were compared per

204 group and time point using a one-way analysis
205 of variance (ANOVA). To evaluate the effect of the interventions in honey
206 production, the mean values recorded from each group at the harvesting season
207 (Sept. 08) were also compared using one-way ANOVA. Where necessary,
208 ANOVA was followed by Bonferroni or Tamhane *post hoc* tests, depending on
209 the homogeneity of variance in each case (determined using Levene's test).

210 To assess the effect of the interventions in the colonies we ran a paired *t* test
211 comparing the percentage of infected bees before and after interventions both in
212 autumn 07 and in spring 08.

213 A Student's *t* test was used to compare the prevalence of *N. apis* versus *N.*
214 *ceranae* in individual forager bee samples.

215 In all statistical studies, differences were considered significant when $\alpha \leq 0.05$.

216 Spearman's rank correlation test was used to determine the degree of dependence
217 between the percentage of *N. ceranae* infected bees and: (a) population size; (b)
218 the amount of brood cells; (c) honey production in the corresponding hives; and
219 (d) the amount of fumagillin consumed in the case of treated colonies (groups 1T,
220 2T and 4T in autumn 2007, and groups 2T and 4T in spring 2008). The same
221 analysis was performed with the percentage of *N. apis* infected bees. These
222 correlations were performed in function of the percentage of infected bees from
223 November 2007 and July 2008. Correlations were considered significant when $\alpha \leq$
224 0.05 (2-tailed test).

225 All analyses were carried out using SPSS 18.0 software.

226

227 **3. RESULTS**

228 **3.1. Monitoring of *Nosema* spp. infection in experimental colonies**

229 **3.1.1. Detection of infection (composite samples)**

230 **Forager bees.** The 50 composite forager bee samples analysed all tested positive
231 for *N. ceranae* infection at the beginning of the assay in September 2007, with 25
232 (50%) also exhibiting co-infection with *N. apis*. Analysis of the composite forager
233 bee samples throughout the year (Sept. 2007 to Dec. 2008) primarily revealed
234 infection by *N. ceranae* alone in the *Nosema*-positive colonies (314 out of 413
235 *Nosema*-positive samples; 76%), although co-infection with *N. apis* was also
236 detected (97 out of 413 *Nosema*-positive samples; 23.5%). By contrast, infection
237 by *N. apis* alone was only detected in 2 colonies (0.5%). Both microsporidia were
238 detected throughout the year and while the presence of *N. ceranae* was constant,
239 that of *N. apis* was more evident in the autumn and spring months (Supplementary
240 data Figure S1). All of the untreated colonies remained infected throughout the
241 assay, whereas *Nosema* was not detected in some of the treated colonies after
242 intervention (Figure 1).

243 **House bees.** Before the interventions in October 2007, *N. ceranae* infection was
244 evident in 43 of the colonies (86%), 2 of which (4%) were co-infected with *N.*
245 *apis* (two colonies of group 2T). No infection was detected in 5 colonies (10%)
246 after analysing the composite house bee samples (1 colony of group 1T, 3
247 colonies of group 2T and 1 colony of group CS). Based on the analysis of
248 composite house bee samples ($n \geq 30$ bees) before and after the autumn 2007 and

249 spring 2008 interventions, the percentage of colonies infected by *Nosema* spp.
250 was evaluated (Figure 2A).

251 **3.1.2. Percentage of infected bees before and after intervention**

252 **Forager bees.** The percentage of foragers infected with *Nosema* spp. before
253 intervention (October 2007) differed significantly between groups (ANOVA, $F =$
254 4.39 , $P = 0.006$; Figure 3, Supplementary data Table 1), with fewer infected bees
255 detected in the CS group with respect to groups 1T and 4T. However, after the
256 treatment was applied in the corresponding groups (November 2007), groups 1T,
257 2T and 4T exhibited significantly fewer infected forager bees (ANOVA, $F = 21.1$,
258 $P \leq 0.001$; Figure 3, Supplementary data Table 1, Supplementary data Figure S3)
259 than in groups CS and C.

260 As for the effect of the treatment against *Nosema* in each group in autumn 2007, it
261 significantly decreased the proportion of infected foragers in groups 1T, 2T and
262 4T from October to November (paired t test, $P < 0.001$). Conversely, the rates of
263 infection tended to increase from October to November in the untreated colonies
264 (groups CS and C: Figure 3), although this effect was not statistically significant
265 (paired t test, $P > 0.05$).

266 In May 2008, before the spring intervention in the corresponding colonies,
267 significant differences in infected foragers were detected between groups
268 (ANOVA, $F = 4.5$, $P = 0.006$). Group 2T had a smaller proportion of infected
269 bees ($P < 0.05$) than the control CS and C groups. Similarly, in early July, after
270 treatment application in the corresponding groups (*i.e.* 2T and 4T) and syrup
271 supply in group CS, percentage of infected bees presented significant differences

272 between groups (ANOVA, $F = 46.3$, $P < 0.001$), showing groups 2T and 4T an
273 infection rate significantly lower than the registered in control groups CS and C.
274 In the 1T group that received fumagillin in autumn 2007 but not in spring 2008,
275 we detected a significantly lower proportion of infected bees than in the untreated
276 groups CS ($P = 0.001$) and C ($P = 0.01$), although there were significantly more
277 infected bees than in groups 2T ($P < 0.001$) and 4T ($P < 0.001$: Figure 3,
278 Supplementary data Table 1).

279 An intra-group evaluation of the percentage of bees infected in spring 2008
280 revealed a trend to decrease in the 2T and 4T groups and to increase in the 1T, CS
281 and C groups between May and July (Figure 3, Supplementary data Table 1,
282 Supplementary data Figure S4). However, no significant differences were
283 detected within any of the experimental groups (paired t test, $P > 0.05$) before or
284 after treatment (2T and 4T) or syrup (CS) administration, or in the colonies that
285 received no intervention (1T and C).

286 Moreover, in the treated colonies, syrup with fumagillin consumption was
287 inversely proportional to the percentage of *Nosema*-infected bees (autumn
288 intervention, $r = -0.54$, $P = 0.021$; spring intervention, $r = -0.69$, $P < 0.001$;
289 Spearman's rank correlation). In addition, there was a significantly higher
290 prevalence of *N. ceranae* over *N. apis* when the two *Nosema* species were
291 analysed in individual forager bees (Figure 3), both in autumn ($F = 54.9$, $P <$
292 0.001 ; Student's t -test) and in spring ($F = 19.3$, $P < 0.001$, Student's t -test).

293 **House bees.** As indicated in the methods, only a small group of colonies that were
294 infected after the composite sample analysis were randomly selected to evaluate

295 the rate of infection. Less than 5% of bees were infected in all the colonies
296 analyzed from the treated groups after the intervention in October 2007 and May
297 2008, except for colony 4T-6, in which 35% of the bees were infected with *N.*
298 *cerranae* after the autumn treatment. In the untreated colonies the levels of
299 infection were in the range of 10% to 30% after the autumn and spring
300 interventions (Figure 2B).

301 **3.2. Adult bee population size and brood production**

302 At several stages during the study, the population size was larger in the colonies
303 in which *Nosema* infection was controlled than in the untreated colonies. At the
304 start of the study (October 2007) the adult bee populations were of equivalent
305 sizes in all groups (ANOVA, $F = 0.3$, $P = 0.8$). However, a more pronounced and
306 sustained drop in population size was observed in groups CS and C from the
307 beginning of the study until February 2008, when the treated populations 1T, 2T
308 and 4T were significantly larger (ANOVA, $F = 17.8$, $P < 0.001$) than the control
309 groups (CS and C: Figure 4A, Supplementary data Table 2). Throughout the
310 spring and summer months (from April to August), significantly larger
311 populations were found in the treated 2T and 4T groups than in the control groups
312 (CS and C, $P < 0.001$). Indeed, even the colonies in group 1T (only treated in
313 autumn 2007) were significantly more populated than those of the C group in July
314 ($P = 0.04$) and August ($P = 0.02$). The maximum population was recorded at the
315 same time in all the groups (July 2008: Figure 4A, Supplementary data Table 2).
316 A significant negative correlation was detected between population size and the
317 percentage of *N. cerranae* infected bees of any colony in July 2008 ($r = - 0.57$, P

318 = 0.001; Spearman's rank correlation), while such correlation was not observed in
319 November 2007 ($r = - 0.32$, $P = 0.07$; Spearman's rank correlation). No
320 correlation was found between the percentage of *N. apis* infected bees and the
321 population size in November 2007 ($r = - 0.26$; $P = 0.12$) or July 2008 ($r = - 0.14$;
322 $P = 0.23$; Spearman's rank correlation).

323 Like the adult bee population, the brood area was larger in the treated groups at
324 several time points during the assay. Initially (October 2007), brood rearing was
325 similar between groups (ANOVA, $F = 0.6$, $P = 0.3$), although significant
326 differences appeared in February (ANOVA, $F = 4.6$, $P = 0.003$) and April 2008
327 (ANOVA, $F = 5.4$, $P = 0.001$) that were associated with a significant increase in
328 brood cells in the 2T and 4T groups as compared with control CS and C groups
329 (Figure 4B, Supplementary data Table 2). In May 2008, group C produced
330 significantly less brood than groups 2T ($P = 0.03$) and 4T ($P = 0.03$), although one
331 month later (June 2008) brood production was only greater in group 2T with
332 respect to the control groups CS ($P = 0.002$) and C ($P = 0.004$). At the end of the
333 trial, in October 2008, group 2T again contained significantly more brood cells
334 than the control CS ($P = 0.01$) and C groups ($P = 0.007$). The brood production in
335 the treated colonies (1T, 2T and 4T) peaked in June, while that of the control
336 colonies CS and C reached its highest level in July (Figure 4B, Supplementary
337 data Table 2).

338 No significant correlation was observed between the proportion of bees
339 parasitized by *N. ceranae* and the amount of brood cells in November 2007 ($r =$
340 0.28 , $P = 0.11$; Spearman's rank correlation) or July 2008 ($r = - 0.19$, $P = 0.27$;

341 Spearman's rank correlation), as resulted with the proportion of *N. apis*
342 parasitized bees and the brood in November 2007 ($r = 0.34$; $P = 0.21$; Spearman's
343 rank correlation) or July 2008 ($r = -0.07$; $P = 0.67$; Spearman's rank correlation).
344 On the other hand, the ratio of brood cells to adult bee combs (NC/P) in July was
345 significantly greater in the control CS and C groups than in the treated groups
346 (ANOVA, $F = 6.7$, $P < 0.001$; Figure 4C). By contrast, in August only the CS
347 group exhibited a significantly higher NC/P ratio with respect to groups 1T ($P =$
348 0.004), 2T ($P = 0.03$) and 4T ($P = 0.006$).

349 **3.3. Natural queen supersedure and colony mortality**

350 Only 4 of the 50 colonies underwent natural queen supersedure during the study:
351 2 colonies in group 1T (colonies 1T-6 and 1T-8), 1 from group 4T (4T-9) and 1
352 from the C group (C-7) in June 2008, while colony C-3 changed its queen in July
353 2008 (Supplementary data Figure S1).

354 Several colonies died before the end of the study in December 2008. One colony
355 from group 4T collapsed in February 2008 with signs of chalkbrood disease.
356 Another colony from group 4T and one of group 1T died in July and May 2008
357 respectively after one month producing only drone brood (queenless or laying
358 worker colony; Supplementary data Figure S1).

359 Three CS colonies died in the winter-spring of 2008, one with symptoms of
360 American Foulbrood (AFB) prior to collapse, while no bees remained inside the
361 colony after collapse in the other 2. In group C, 3 colonies died during the same
362 period, 2 of which only produced drone brood before collapse. In these colonies
363 no death or crawling bees around the hives or faecal marks were detected.

364 In the analyses prior to collapse, all the dead colonies contained a percentage of
365 *N. ceranae* infected forager bees of over 45% (range 45-95%).

366 In the period following interventions in the colonies, 2 colonies from the 1T group
367 collapsed, exhibiting symptoms of AFB in January 2009. Of the untreated
368 colonies, 4 CS and 3 C colonies died between July 2009 and October 2010,
369 leaving no bees in the hive (Supplementary data Figure S1). Thus, in December
370 2010 the percentage of surviving colonies was 70% in group 1T, 100% in group
371 2T, 80% in group 4T, 30% in group CS and 40% in group C.

372 **3.4. Honey production**

373 In general, the colonies in groups 2T and 4T tended to produce more honey than
374 those of the other groups. In particular, colonies in group 2T produced
375 significantly more honey (21.2 ± 7.3 kg honey/colony) than those in group C (8.9
376 ± 5.9 kg h/c, $P = 0.04$). Moreover, colonies of group 4T (24.1 ± 7.3 kg h/c) were
377 significantly more productive than those of groups CS (11.5 ± 5.1 kg h/c, $P =$
378 0.03) and C ($P = 0.009$). The colonies in group 1T produced less honey ($14.5 \pm$
379 12.1 kg h/c) than the colonies in the other treated groups but more than those in
380 the control groups (Figure 5A), although these effects failed to reach statistical
381 significance ($P > 0.05$).

382 The amount of honey produced by each colony in September 2008 was
383 significantly related to the percentage of *N. ceranae* parasitized bees in the
384 corresponding hives in July 2008 ($r = - 0.51$, $P = 0.002$; Spearman's rank
385 correlation), but not in November 2007 ($r = - 0.29$, $P = 0.09$; Spearman's rank
386 correlation). On the other hand, no correlation was found between the honey

387 production and the percentage of *N. apis* parasitized bees in November 2007 ($r = -$
388 0.28, $P = 0.11$; Spearman's rank correlation) or July 2008 ($r = - 0.21$, $P = 0.14$;
389 Spearman's rank correlation).

390 The colonies that died before the harvesting season (2 colonies from group 4T, 3
391 colonies in group CS and 3 colonies from group C) were not considered when
392 calculating the mean honey production of each group (Figure 5B).

393

394 **4. Discussion**

395 In this field study, we confirm the negative influence of *Nosema* infection on adult
396 honey bee population size and brood production, and we show that when these
397 microsporidia are not controlled, infection provokes a significant decrease in
398 honey production. As *N. ceranae* was the dominant species in the infected
399 colonies throughout the study, the observed effects may principally be attributed
400 to this microsporidium. However, although *N. apis* showed a small prevalence
401 within the infected colonies and was not constantly present in them throughout the
402 assay, a negative effect of this microsporidium over the colonies health cannot be
403 discarded.

404 The number of adult bees, sealed brood and the amount of honey produced are
405 valuable indicators of hive health [54]. In our experimental conditions, the health
406 status of the colonies was worse when they were highly infected with *N. ceranae*
407 than when infection was controlled, suggesting that this microsporidium may have
408 deleterious effects at the colony level, as suggested previously [28,55-57]. It is
409 also worth mentioning that part of the non-treated colonies died leaving no bees in

410 the hive at the moment of collapse, coinciding with signs described in a preceding
411 study [28]. Therefore, the parameters here presented regarding hive health status,
412 taken together with other recently shown [52,58,59], may be considered as sub-
413 clinical signs of nosemosis type C.

414 At the beginning of the study the percentage of infected foragers in CS colonies
415 was significantly lower than that of groups 1T and 4T, but this parameter tended
416 to increase from October to November, by which time it was significantly greater
417 than that of treated groups. Therefore, the difference observed at the beginning of
418 the assay is unlikely to have significantly altered the results obtained after the
419 interventions in autumn and spring.

420 The percentage of *Nosema*-infected forager bees is thought to be a potentially
421 useful indicator of the extent of colony infection [22,28,60-61]. The proportion of
422 *Nosema*-infected forager bees in our colonies revealed significantly stronger
423 infection than in the untreated colonies (groups CS and C) after the autumn and
424 spring interventions, which may account for the observed differences in the fitness
425 parameters like population size, brood production and honey production from
426 those of the treated colonies (groups 1T, 2T and 4T). Moreover, after the spring
427 intervention we detected a significant negative correlation between *N. ceranae*
428 infection and the size of worker population, as seen previously [28,56]. Indeed,
429 there were significantly fewer bee combs in the spring and summer months in the
430 colonies with the strongest *N. ceranae* infection (groups CS and C). Colony
431 population size depends mainly on the worker bee life span [18] and as *N.*
432 *ceranae* has a negative impact on this parameter in honey bees [34,35,62-63], it

433 probably exerts a direct negative impact on colony size in accordance with our
434 results.

435 *Nosema* infection was less prevalent in house bees than in forager bees, as
436 reported previously [28,50-51,64]. As the probability of acquiring infection is
437 likely to increase with age and novel diseases are more often picked up by
438 foragers, young workers should be less susceptible to infection [65]. A direct link
439 has been reported between infection levels in forager and house bees [66-67], but
440 in the present assay we failed to establish such a correlation as the number of
441 colonies in which the proportion of infected house bees was analysed was very
442 limited. However, a subsequent study suggested that the interior bees may more
443 accurately reflect the level of the infection within the colony [52]. In our
444 experimental conditions, forager bee infection rates of at least 45% were evident
445 in all the collapsed colonies, while the percentage of infected house bees in
446 collapsed colonies, only measured in colonies CS-7 and 4T-6, was 20% and 35%,
447 respectively. However, infection levels of 35% were also recorded in house bees
448 in a colony that did not collapse (colony C-3) in July. This particular colony
449 underwent natural queen supersedure in July, which may have subsequently
450 decreased its infection rate and thus, the likelihood of collapse [52]. Yet as the
451 infection rate was not monitored after this time point, this hypothesis could not be
452 corroborated. In colony C-6, which also underwent queen supersedure in June, the
453 infection rate in house bees after one month was lower than that observed in the
454 treated colonies (15%), while the forager bees exhibited a very high level of
455 *Nosema* infection (75%). Thus, the influence of queen replacement on *Nosema*

456 infection appears to primarily affect the house bee population, and the foragers to
457 a lesser extent, although again this hypothesis could not be confirmed as infection
458 rates were not subsequently measured.

459 Brood production was not correlated with infection levels, although less infected
460 colonies had significantly more brood cells than those in highly infected groups at
461 different time points throughout the study, consistent with earlier studies of
462 *Nosema*-infected colonies [28,44,68]. Furthermore, brood production was slower
463 in the untreated groups (groups CS and C), peaking in July, than in groups 1T, 2T
464 and 4T, which began growing earlier and reached maximum levels one month
465 earlier (June).

466 Adult bee population size and brood production are correlated [56,69-71], and as
467 mentioned above, increased bee mortality has been described in *N. ceranae*-
468 infected bees. The smaller populations observed in strongly infected colonies may
469 therefore reflect a combination of decreased brood rearing and increased forager
470 death in these colonies. Furthermore, thermoregulation and brood food production
471 may be dysregulated in infected colonies with small populations [72], resulting in
472 reduced brood rearing efficiency [73,74]. Nurse bees begin to forage precociously
473 in response to high forager death rates [72,75-77]. While this strategy restores the
474 proportion of foragers in the population, it also shortens the overall lifespan of
475 adult bees [78-80], as well as their effectiveness and resilience as foragers [81].
476 This strategy also reduces the time each bee can dedicate to colony growth and
477 brood production. Thus, when the rate of brood production is insufficient to

478 replace the forager bees lost due to *Nosema* infection, the decline of the colony
479 may accelerate [28,77].

480 Colonies with high levels of *N. ceranae* infection throughout the study (groups CS
481 and C) had significantly more brood cells relative to the adult bee population
482 during the summer months (July and August). As the bee colony grows, a
483 decrease in the ratio of brood to bees has been reported previously [71,82,83], as
484 observed during the evolution of the colonies with a milder degree of infection
485 here (groups 1T, 2T and 4T). By contrast, strongly infected colonies (groups CS
486 and C) did not grow at the same rate as treated colonies, and they did not
487 experience a similar decrease in the proportion of brood to bees. The higher ratio
488 of brood to bees in severely infected colonies may reflect the increased rearing
489 effort in the colony in an attempt to replace the worker bees lost due to *Nosema*
490 infection [44], although further studies will be necessary to confirm this
491 hypothesis.

492 As honey production is generally correlated with the number of worker brood
493 cells and the worker population [19,84], larger colonies tend to store more honey
494 [20]. In addition, nectar foragers from larger colonies visit more flowers on each
495 trip, with a shorter handling time per flower when compared to those from small
496 colonies [85]. However, *Nosema* may negatively influence the flight ability of
497 infected honey bee foragers [86,87] and as such, the value of the nectar and pollen
498 resources will depend on the status of the colony [89]. According to our results,
499 colonies with more severe *N. ceranae* infection, with smaller colonies and brood

500 area, have lower yields of honey, as reported previously for *N. apis*-infected
501 colonies [27,47,70].

502 Although there was no correlation between *N. ceranae* infection and variations in
503 colony strength or increased winter mortality in a recent study [90], in our
504 experimental conditions this microsporidium was very pathogenic to honey bee
505 colonies, as evident by its impact on population size, the amount of brood and
506 honey production. These conflicting findings may reflect differences in the
507 experimental procedures used, as different methods and time points were used
508 when measuring infection, colony strength and other parameters related to colony
509 health. Accordingly, it may be necessary to standardize the procedures to evaluate
510 *Nosema* infection in honey bee colonies in order to accurately compare the results
511 from different studies and regions, and to better understand the differences in the
512 epidemiology and pathology of this microsporidium worldwide.

513 The treatment used against *Nosema* in the present study (Fumidil B®) showed to
514 be successful at temporarily reduce *N. ceranae* infection levels in the colonies, as
515 demonstrated previously [52,91], and allowed us to compare the health status of
516 strongly and mildly infected colonies.

517 Collapsed colonies (2 in group 4T, 3 in group CS and 3 in group C) exhibited
518 severe *N. ceranae* infection prior to collapse, consistent with previous reports
519 [31,32]. The collapse of treated colonies in group 4T may have occurred due to
520 poor fumagillin consumption and hence, limited efficacy [52]. Alternatively, in-
521 hive conditions in this group may have been severely disturbed due to the
522 administration of fumagillin in winter time (unlike groups 1T and 2T), triggering

523 a deadly infection by this microsporidium. Otherwise, as this group received the
524 treatment more frequently, a negative impact of this molecule over colony health
525 may have occurred [92], but this suggestion should be more studied. One of the
526 collapsed colonies of group 4T was affected by chalkbrood disease, while another
527 colony from the CS group that died exhibited symptoms of foulbrood disease. *N.*
528 *ceranae* infection in these colonies may have provoked the outbreaks of stress-
529 related diseases such as chalkbrood [61] and foulbrood disease. However, the
530 surviving colonies in the CS and C control groups presented high levels of *N.*
531 *ceranae* infection throughout the study, remaining alive but undergoing the effects
532 of a chronic disease, as demonstrated by the reduced levels of fitness components
533 such as colony size, brood rearing and honey production.

534 Despite the remarkable impact of *Nosema* infection on beekeeping economics
535 [26,47,48], this effect is often underestimated by beekeepers [93]. However, in
536 our experimental conditions *N. ceranae* infection was highly pathogenic to honey
537 bee colonies, as witnessed by sub-clinical signs such as significant decreases in
538 colony size, brood rearing capacity, honey production and, as reported previously
539 [31,58], a decrease in the rate of survival. The study revealed that the control of
540 *Nosema* in autumn and spring could be enough to mitigate these negative effects
541 of nosemosis type C on colony health and productivity, which in turn may affect
542 beekeeping profitability and have dramatic consequences for pollination of crops
543 and in natural ecosystems. As treatments for *Nosema* are currently unavailable in
544 many countries, further studies of potential treatments or beekeeping techniques

545 are urgently required to combat the rapid spread of this dangerous emergent
546 disease.

547

548 **Competing interests**

549 The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

550

551 **Authors' contributions**

552 MH RMH AM conceived and designed the experiments. CB MH RMH performed
553 the experiments and analyzed the data. LB CB MH performed the statistical
554 analysis. CB MH RMH wrote the paper. All authors read and approved the final
555 manuscript.

556

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856 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

857 **Figure 1.** Percentage of colonies infected by *Nosema* spp. during the assay, in
858 function of the analysis of composite forager bee samples ($n \geq 30$ bees per
859 sample). The time points at which fumagillin (arrows) and sugar-syrup (stars)
860 were administered are indicated.

861 **Figure 2. *Nosema* spp. infection of house bees**

862 **A:** Percentage of colonies infected by *Nosema* spp. in each group before and after
863 the interventions in autumn 2007 and spring 2008 based on the PCR analysis of
864 the composite samples of house bees. The experimental groups of colonies were
865 established as follows: group 1T (treatment in autumn 2007), group 2T (treatment
866 in autumn 2007 and spring 2008), group 4T (treatment in autumn 2007, winter,
867 spring and summer 2008), group CS (sugar syrup in autumn 2007, winter, spring
868 and summer 2008) and group C (unmanaged colonies).

869 **B:** Individual PCR analyses ($n = 20$ house bees) in randomly selected colonies,
870 and the corresponding results when composite samples from the same colonies
871 were analysed ($n \geq 30$ house bees). Hyphens indicate no PCR signal for this
872 *Nosema* species in the individual bees analysed.

873 **Figure 3.** Percentage of individual *Nosema*-infected forager bees per group ($n =$
874 200 bees individually analyzed per group and time point; *i.e.* 20 bees from each of
875 the 10 colonies of every group). Analyses were performed in autumn 2007 (pre-
876 and post-intervention) and spring 2008 (pre- and post-intervention). Asterisk
877 indicates significant differences found ($P < 0.01$) in the pre-post intervention
878 interval.

879 **Figure 4.** Data collected from each colony group throughout the study.

880 **A:** Average number of bee combs per group per month.

881 **B:** Average number of brood cells per group per month.

882 **C:** Ratio of brood cells to bee combs in each group throughout the study.

883 **Figure 5.** Honey production in the colonies studied.

884 **A:** Average honey production (kg) per group upon harvesting (September 2008)

885 **B:** Number of productive colonies per group in the harvesting season (September
886 2008).

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902 **SUPPLEMENTARY DATA LEGENDS**

903 **Supplementary Data Table 1.** Percentage of parasitized forager bees per group
904 before and after the interventions in autumn 2007 and spring 2008. Significant
905 differences between groups were determined for each period.

906 Footnotes:

907 Significant difference with respect to CS: ($P = 0.007$)^a; ($P \leq 0.006$)^b; ($P \leq 0.001$)^c; ($P \leq 0.001$)^e; (P
908 ≤ 0.001)^g; ($P = 0.04$)ⁱ; ($P = 0.001$)^m; ($P \leq 0.001$)^o; ($P \leq 0.001$)^q.

909 Significant difference with respect to C: ($P \leq 0.001$)^d; ($P \leq 0.001$)^f; ($P \leq 0.001$)^h; ($P = 0.02$)^j; ($P =$
910 0.01)ⁿ; ($P \leq 0.001$)^p; ($P \leq 0.001$)^r.

911 Significant difference with respect to 1T: ($P \leq 0.001$)^k; ($P \leq 0.001$)^l.

912 **Supplementary Data Table 2.** Number of bee combs (\pm s.d.) and number of
913 brood cells (\pm s.d.) per group in each period.

914 **Supplementary Data Figure 1.** PCR amplification of forager bee composite
915 samples ($n \geq 30$ bees per sample) throughout the study and the data describing
916 other pathologies detected, natural queen supersedure events and colony collapse.

917 **Supplementary Data Figure S2.** Map of the area where the experimental
918 apiaries were located (Source: screenshot of GoogleTM Earth).

919 **Supplementary Data Figure S3.** Mean proportion of infected forager bees ($n =$
920 20 bees per colony) before and after interventions in autumn 2007 for each group.
921 Asterisk indicates significant differences ($P < 0.001$) in the pre-post intervention
922 interval.

923 **Supplementary Data Figure S4.** Mean proportion of infected forager bees ($n =$
924 20 bees) before and after interventions in spring 2008 in each group. No

925 significant differences ($P > 0.05$) were detected in any group in the pre-post
926 intervention interval.

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944 **TABLES**

945 **Table 1.** Chronology of interventions in all colonies (FB = Forager Bees; HB =
 946 House Bees; ALL = All groups). The experimental groups of colonies were
 947 established as follows: group 1T (treatment in autumn 2007), group 2T (treatment
 948 in autumn 2007 and spring 2008), group 4T (treatment in autumn 2007, winter,
 949 spring and summer 2008), group CS (sugar syrup in autumn 2007, winter, spring
 950 and summer 2008) and group C (unmanaged colonies).

INTERVENTIONS IN THE COLONIES	Sep 07	Oct 07	Nov 07	Jan 08	Feb 08	Apr 08	May 08	Jun 08	Jul 08	Aug 08	Sept 08	Oct 08	Nov 08	Dec 08
Fumagillin application		1T 2T 4T		4T			2T 4T			4T				
Syrup application		CS		CS			CS			CS				
FB collection and PCR analysis of composite samples	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL		ALL		ALL	ALL	ALL			ALL
FB collection and PCR analysis of individual bee samples		ALL	ALL				ALL		ALL					
HB collection and PCR analysis of composite samples		ALL	ALL				ALL		ALL					
HB collection and PCR analysis of individual bee samples		ALL	ALL				ALL		ALL					
Data collection of adult bee population and brood rearing		ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL		ALL	ALL	ALL
Data collection of honey production											ALL			

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Figure 1

A

B

GROUP	COLONY	PERIOD	PCR Result COMPOSITE SAMPLES (n ≥ 30 bees)	INDIVIDUAL HOUSE BEES INFECTED (n = 20 bees)		
				<i>N. ceranae</i>	<i>N. apis</i>	<i>N. ceranae + N. apis</i>
1T	1T-3	AUT-POST	<i>N. ceranae</i>	-	-	-
	1T-6	SPR-POST	<i>N. ceranae</i>	-	-	-
	1T-7	SPR-POST	<i>N. ceranae + N. apis</i>	-	-	-
2T	2T-7	AUT-POST	<i>N. ceranae</i>	-	-	-
	2T-6	SPR-POST	<i>N. ceranae</i>	1/20 (5%)	-	-
	2T-9	SPR-POST	<i>N. ceranae</i>	-	-	-
4T	4T-6	AUT-POST	<i>N. ceranae + N. apis</i>	6/20 (30%)	-	1/20 (5%)
CS	CS-2	AUT-POST	<i>N. ceranae</i>	2/20 (10%)	-	-
		SPR-POST	<i>N. ceranae</i>	2/20 (10%)	-	-
	CS-7	AUT-POST	<i>N. ceranae</i>	2/20 (10%)	-	-
		SPR-POST	<i>N. ceranae</i>	4/20 (20%)	-	-
C	C-3	AUT-POST	<i>N. ceranae</i>	2/20 (10%)	1/20 (5%)	-
		SPR-POST	<i>N. ceranae</i>	6/20 (30%)	-	-
	C-6	AUT-POST	<i>N. ceranae</i>	2/20 (10%)	-	-
		SPR-POST	<i>N. ceranae</i>	3/20 (15%)	-	-

Figure 2

Autumn
pre-intervention (October 2007) post-intervention (November 2007)

Spring
pre-intervention (May 2008) post-intervention (July 2008)

N. ceranae
 N. apis
 N. apis + N. ceranae
 Negative

Figure 3

A

B

C

Figure 4

A

Figure 5

INTERVENTIONS IN THE COLONIES	Sep 07	Oct 07	Nov 07	Jan 08	Feb 08	Apr 08	May 08	Jun 08	Jul 08	Aug 08	Sept 08	Oct 08	Nov 08	Dec 08
Fumagillin application		1T 2T 4T		4T			2T 4T			4T				
Syrup application		CS		CS			CS			CS				
FB collection and PCR analysis of composite samples	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL		ALL		ALL	ALL	ALL			ALL
FB collection and PCR analysis of individual bee samples		ALL	ALL				ALL		ALL					
HB collection and PCR analysis of composite samples		ALL	ALL				ALL		ALL					
HB collection and PCR analysis of individual bee samples		ALL	ALL				ALL		ALL					
Data collection of adult bee population and brood rearing		ALL		ALL	ALL	ALL								
Data collection of honey production											ALL			

Figure 6

Additional files provided with this submission:

Additional file 1: Response to Reviewer 1_VR.doc, 1467K

<http://www.veterinaryresearch.org/imedia/5688173538004899/supp1.doc>

Additional file 2: Response to Reviewer 2_VR.doc, 1455K

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